

International Conference on **ICGB 2017** Green Banking Perceptions and Challenges

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A Study on Customer Psychology towards Green Banking: With Special References to Uttara Kannada District

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Abstract—Banking sector is one of the emerging sector in today's Indian economy. The banking sector influence to economic growth and development of the country both in terms of quality and quantity, there by adopting various strategies for economic growth. One such area is Green Banking. Green banking is a normal bank which encourages to the electronic transaction by reducing a quantity of paper work. It enables a healthy environmental condition. To achieve the prescribed objectives of this study, the data has to be collect in a significant manner. This research can be done by primary method and secondary method. Finally, green banking can play a significant role in implementing the broader concepts like sustainable economic development.

Keywords: Psychology, Sustainable, Traditional Banking, Environment, Respondent

INTRODUCTION

The functions of financial institutions like banks are restricted to accept deposits and to provide loans and advances. Modern information technology has provided a up step towards innovation and transformation. Modern banking is also known as innovative banking. Banks are on the urge of major transformations, where the single largest force behind the transformation is information technology. Thus green banking has been a important part of Indian banking sector. It is also proved that the security level will be so high compared to the traditional banking systems. The customers will perform the transactions in the banks unless and until they were satisfied about the safety and security. Since a last few years, banks are registered a impressive growth towards green banking services and the response from the customers also a noticeable one.

MEANING

Green banking is a normal bank which encourages to the electronic transaction by reducing a quantity of paper work. It enables a healthy environmental condition. Banks benefitted from this as it minimize the carbon foot prints and protect our natural resources. Its products like debit card, credit card, online banking etc.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study is to examine customer psychology of green banking in Uttar Kannada district. They are as follows:

1. To understand the different products and services provided by the banks under green banking.

2. To examine the psychology aspects of the public towards green banking.
3. To make a suggestion to development of green banking in Uttar Kannada district.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

To achieve the prescribed objectives of this study, the data has to be collect in a significant manner. This research can be done by primary method and secondary method.

PRIMARY METHOD

- Questionnaire method: this method is a research instrument including a set of questions and other prompts for the intention of collecting information's from the respondents.
- Personal interview: It is also called as a face to face survey method i.e. utilized when a specific target population is involved. The main advantage of conducting a personal interview survey is to analyze the responses of the public together more and deeper.

SECONDARY METHOD

This method includes published and non-published sources. Published sources like journals, magazines, books and online resource. So that we can get numerous knowledge about the situation.

GREEN BANKING PRODUCTS

- Debit card
- Credit card
- Online banking
- Mobile banking
- Solar energy

DEBIT CARD

Debit card or bank card is also known as plastic payment card which can be used for payments when making purchases. In many areas the use of debit card has become so widespread they are entirely replacing the facility of cheques and in some cases cash transactions also. Unlike credit card payments, which are made by debit cards are immediately transferred from the designated bank account. Debit card also allow for quick withdrawal of cash performs as the ATM cards for withdrawals.

CREDIT CARD

A credit card is a plastic card issued to customers to enable them to make the payment based on their promise to the bank to pay them for the amounts so paid plus other agreed charges. When an individual uses credit card to make the purchases, he or she is authorizing the bank to make their payments on behalf of them.

MOBILE BANKING

Mobile banking is a powerful media in modern banking era, which allows its user for the act of doing financial transactions on a mobile device like cell phones, tablets, notes etc.. This activity is so easy that the banks will create their own applications and allow their customers to logged in. Once the customer is logged into the app, the bank will starts to sent information regarding their accounts and it also facilitates its customers to make banking transactions in their mobile.

ONLINE BANKING

Online banking or internet banking is a facility which allows a user to execute financial transactions by internet. This facility offers just about every services available by a local branch which includes deposits, which is done by online or by mail etc.

SOLAR ENERGY

In green banks there will be a higher usage of solar energy products instead of electricity power. It will reduce the cost and expenditure. We can easily understand that solar energy as a energy obtained from the sun. We can put this energy to work for us in many ways.

ADVANTAGES OF GREEN BANKING

Every concept has its own advantages and disadvantages. The ratio of both will be different. Concern to G-banking concept advantages will be higher than its disadvantages.

They are:

1. The day to day expenses of banking services is lower for the banks.
2. It provides convenience to customers as they need not to go to the bank premises.
3. Anyone can get funds at any time at any place.
4. The credit card and debit card facility enables the customers to obtain discount from retail outlets.
5. Transfer of funds can be easily done through G-banking services.

FINDINGS

Respondents reaction, insight and psychology towards Green banking:

Table 1

Questions	Respondent's Reactions	
	Yes	No
1. Are you aware of Green banking services provided by your bank?	55%	45%
2. Do you want development in green banking services ?	85%	15%
3. Are you contented with the Green banking services provided by your bank?	60%	40%
4. Should traditional banking replaced with green banking ?	70%	30%
5. Is future of green banking is sustainable ?	80%	20%
6. Do you use green banking services ?	75%	25%

From the above details, we can conclude that the customers are literally using green banking services and their insight towards green banking is positive. There is bright future for green banking in Uttar Kannada district of appropriate policy is adopted to upgrade technology.

- It is being traced that 55% of the bank customers are aware of green banking concept.
- The remaining 45% of customers are not aware of green banking as they literally happy with the traditional method.
- It is also true that more than 30% of customers are demanding for the traditional method.
- A certain portion of customers are not willing to transform to green banking as they are well educated as well as also aware of green banking.

Responses regarding basis for not using green banking services provided by the banks.

Table 2

Questions	Reactions	
	Yes	No
1. Lack of operating knowledge	30%	70%
2. Awareness about green banking services	37%	63%
3. Waste of time	50%	50%

From the above details it is opined that for the reason of lack of knowledge about green banking services most of the customers are not using green banking though majority no of customers are satisfied with the green banking services.

LIMITATIONS

- In view of technicalities it cannot be assume that all the necessary facts and figures have been gathered in the process of study.
- Time frame was the biggest limitation of the study. Related to this study it would be unrealistic to assume that the sufficient amount of information or data has been collected within the timeframe.

- This study and the data collection has been done from a particular geographical area. therefore the finding and conclusions have got their own limitations
- It could not be believe that the respondents have given the correct or accurate information. There may be a chance of misleading.

SUGGESTIONS

Private sector commercial banks as well as Government sector banks are rigorously working on Green Banking strategies for making themselves as more responsible corporate citizen of the Uttar Kannada district. This study tells us that the banks are adopting green banking because of some versatile factors. This study reveals the above findings and the following advice to banks as well as RBI.

- Every bank should focus on all the key benefits of green banking in order to fully implement in U.K. district.
- Every bank should explain all the benefits of green banking to all its customers.
- The RBI or Head offices of the concerned bank should also give importance to protect the environment and explain how various measures under green banking can help to protect the environment.
- Commercial banks should promote its green banking activities to encash environment conscious customers and also to aware share holders that is fully committed to the environment of Karnataka.
- All Head Offices as well as RBI should take all the necessary steps to promote green banking system in their all branches successfully.
- All the bank employees should be properly trained about green banking working scenario.
- All the banks should develop green fund fort polio for the environmental friendly projects with lower interest rates.
- According to the some global surveys on green banking reveals that high demand and high interest rates are 2 important characteristics of green banking loan. So all the banks should prepare for the said situation for capturing the market.
- Finally the commercial banks may be held liable in future for the pollution by its own clients as it they do not upgrade to green banking. So banks in U.K. district should think twice before investing in environmentally harmful projects.

CONCLUSION

Uttara Kannada is one of the several affected district of state environmental pollution. We need to create pressure on certain community to reduce carbon dioxide pollution. On the other hand we have to take strong stance against our internal polluters. As banks indirectly

invests in environment pollution through contributing in different pollutant industries. The RBI has to create steps against all the wrong doin. RBI which has the legal power to shape the behavior of the banks. It will have to force all the banks to implement green banking policy to curb its own environmental pollution giving loans to eco-friendly projects and reducing investments in environmental harmful projects. Thus green banking can play a significant role in implementing the broader concepts like sustainable economic development.

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